

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18825432

Family Communication Patterns as Correlates of Psychosocial Adjustment of Undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi

Raymond D. Tor-Anyiin¹ & Ezekiel A. Hanior², PhD

¹Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling,
Federal College of Education (Technical), Keana, Nigeria
¹raymondtoranyiin@gmail.com ; +2349066998056

²Department of Educational Foundations,
Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria
²ezekielhanior@gmail.com ; +2347037863039

ABSTRACT

This study investigated family communication patterns as correlates of psychosocial adjustment among undergraduates of Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. Guided by six research questions and six corresponding hypotheses, the study adopted a correlational survey design. The population comprised 25,843 undergraduates drawn from eight faculties of the university, from which a sample of 394 students was selected using a multistage sampling procedure. Data were collected using two researcher-developed instruments: the Family Communication Patterns Questionnaire (FCPQ) and the Undergraduates' Psychosocial Adjustment Scale (UPAS), both structured on a four-point Likert scale. The instruments were validated by experts in Guidance and Counselling and Science and Mathematics Education, and yielded reliability coefficients of 0.746 and 0.754 respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was employed to answer research questions and test hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that consensual and pluralistic family communication patterns had significant moderate positive relationships with psychosocial adjustment, while protective and laissez-faire family communication patterns showed significant but weak positive relationships. Based on the findings, it was recommended that parents and guardians adopt more open, supportive, and dialogic communication practices, while universities and counselling centres strengthen family-based counselling, mentorship, and gender- and marital-status-sensitive intervention programmes to enhance undergraduates' psychosocial adjustment.

Keywords: Family Communication Patterns (FCP), Consensual FCP, Pluralistic FCP, Protective FCP, Laissez-Faire FCP, Psychosocial Adjustment.

INTRODUCTION

The psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates has increasingly become a concern. Globally, undergraduates are facing growing psychosocial distress, including stress, anxiety, depression, and difficulty adapting to academic and social demands. Research has consistently documented that stress, anxiety, and depressive symptoms are prevalent among college students worldwide and significantly affect their academic performance, social interactions, and mental health outcomes. For example, Roy, Biswas and Sharma (2025) found widespread psychological distress among undergraduate populations,

highlighting that stress, anxiety, and depression adversely influence students' ability to adapt to university life and maintain healthy social engagement thereby leading to poor psychosocial adjustment. In order to properly understand the growing concern surrounding these psychosocial difficulties among undergraduates, it is necessary to clarify what is meant by psychosocial adjustment and the key processes it entails.

Psychosocial adjustment can be said to be the process of an individual adapting to and functioning effectively within their social environment. It involves the ability to meet the demands of everyday life, maintain relationships, and cope with various challenges and stressors. According to Chane (2024), psychosocial adjustment is the process through which students manage emotional, social, and academic demands, fostering a balance between their psychological well-being and interactions within school environments, peers, and institutional expectations. Among undergraduates, it encompasses their correct functioning and adaptation to their academic activities, interpersonal relationships and the disposition of the right attitudes and emotions as well as an exhibition of acceptable communication skills and social competencies. Given this understanding of psychosocial adjustment, it becomes necessary to examine empirical evidence on how undergraduates across different contexts experience difficulties in achieving such adjustment.

In the United States, a systematic review of undergraduate psychosocial adjustment by Brunsting, Zachry, and Takeuchi (2018) indicated that loneliness, depression, and anxiety are common outcomes that hinder students' sense of belonging and capacity to integrate effectively into campus life. Similar patterns are found in other regions, pointing to psychosocial non-adjustment as a persistent global challenge for higher education institutions. In Nigeria, emerging evidence suggests that psychosocial difficulties are a significant concern for undergraduates. For instance, research by Ogunmodede, Adegunloye, Oguntayo, Ajokpaniowo, Buhari, Bolarinwa, Malomo, and Oyeleke (2023) exploring psychosocial factors among Nigerian university students found notable levels of psychiatric morbidity, with nearly one in four students showing indications of mental health challenges that could be linked to stress, social problems, and emotional difficulties. These global and national patterns of psychosocial difficulty are also evident within specific university settings, including Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

At Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, observable patterns suggest that undergraduates are not immune to these broader trends. Many students demonstrate signs of psychosocial non-adjustment, such as reluctance to participate in class, difficulty sustaining meaningful peer interactions, low confidence in social settings, and poor emotional coping in response to academic and social pressures. These manifestations are troubling because they not only impede academic success but also erode students' capacity to build healthy interpersonal networks and manage life transitions effectively. While psychosocial non-adjustment among undergraduates is clearly multifaceted, existing literature suggests that one of the most influential yet often overlooked factors lies within the family environment, particularly family relationships and communication patterns. Koerner and Fitzpatrick (2012) assert that families are the first social environment in which individuals learn to interact, express emotions, resolve conflicts, and develop a sense of self, making the family a critical determinant of psychosocial adjustment later in life. To better understand how family environments shape undergraduates' psychosocial adjustment, it is important to examine the concept of family communication patterns as a key theoretical framework.

Family communication patterns refer to the consistent and predictable ways in which family members interact and communicate with each other (Koerner & Fitzpatrick, 2012). These authors further posit that family communication patterns come from the process by which families build and exchange social reality. As a result, they are closely related to the most basic social functioning of the family. Family communication patterns, in particular, emerge from the process of co-orientation (which refers to two or more people focusing on and evaluating the same object in their social or material surroundings), without which human connection in general, and family communication in particular, would be impossible. According to Effiong and Usoroh (2020), family communication encompasses more than just verbal

exchanges among family members. It also includes elements such as speech tones, posture, gestures, and facial expressions.

Although family communication patterns are explicitly differentiated, they are not completely independent of each other; a family could be found to be on the high or low continuum of either of the FCPs or maintain a balance. However, the effects of any of the two on a family's communication style is felt with the consequence that one would be latent or both would have to maintain a balance. Koerner and Fitzpatrick (2012) maintained that because the two aspects of conversation orientation and conformity orientation consistently interact with one another, they actually produce four qualitatively distinct family communication patterns. They include; consensual, pluralistic, protective, and laissez-faire family communication patterns.

Consensual family communication pattern is characterized by high levels of both conversation and conformity orientations. According to Koerner and Fitzpatrick (2012), families operating within this pattern encourage open dialogue, allowing members to freely express thoughts, emotions, and opinions, while simultaneously emphasizing adherence to shared family values, rules, and hierarchical authority. This combination creates a structured yet supportive communication environment in which children feel listened to and validated, but are also guided by clear expectations and parental direction. Koerner and Schrodts (2014) further assert that this communication pattern supports healthy family functioning by enabling children to develop both autonomy and a sense of connectedness. Such families help students build critical social and emotional skills, including empathy, emotional regulation, and interpersonal effectiveness. These skills are essential for psychosocial adjustment, particularly in adolescence and early adulthood when identity formation and peer relationships become central to development. Furthermore, Motschnig, Kornacki, and Gamsjäger (2021) highlight that adolescents raised in consensual families tend to exhibit higher levels of psychological well-being, lower instances of behavioural issues, and greater academic motivation. The structure and emotional support provided by consensual communication foster a secure environment in which students feel valued and understood, enhancing their self-esteem and capacity to manage stress. Moreover, the internalization of shared values and social norms prepares them to adapt more effectively to school settings, peer interactions, and other social environments. While the consensual family communication pattern balances open dialogue with clear expectations and parental authority, other families emphasize openness without a corresponding emphasis on conformity, giving rise to the pluralistic communication pattern.

Pluralistic family communication pattern also features high conversation but low conformity. Family members are encouraged to express their individual thoughts and opinions, even if they differ from the prevailing family norms. "This parental attitude leads to family discussions in which opinions are evaluated based on the merit of arguments in their support rather than on which family members espouse them" (Koerner & Fitzpatrick, 2012, p. 140). This can lead to a high degree of independence among family members and the development of autonomy and assertiveness in thinking and behaviour. Moreover, the authors posit that growing up in this type of family can predict poor adjustment and other related outcomes and generally poor communication competence. From a psychosocial perspective, children raised in pluralistic families often demonstrate high social competence, including the ability to engage in meaningful conversations, resolve conflicts through discussion, and appreciate diverse viewpoints (Koerner & Schrodts, 2014). These communication competencies are strongly linked to positive psychosocial outcomes, such as higher self-esteem, academic motivation, and greater resilience (Socha & Yingling, 2010). However, the relationship between pluralistic communication and psychosocial adjustment is complex. While the autonomy it fosters can be adaptive, especially in contexts that value individualism, some research suggests that without adequate emotional regulation and boundaries, children may experience confusion, decision-making stress, or even a lack of clarity in role expectations, which can undermine psychosocial well-being (Koerner & Fitzpatrick, 2012). Thus, although pluralistic patterns promote open-mindedness, they do not inherently guarantee positive adjustment unless balanced with supportive parental guidance and emotional scaffolding. In educational settings, students from pluralistic families may exhibit enhanced critical thinking skills, but their

psychosocial adjustment can vary depending on the consistency and quality of the support systems within both family and school contexts (Lumpe, Wörle, & Zitzmann, 2010). For instance, they might excel in environments that reward autonomy but struggle in highly structured or authoritarian settings that limit discourse. In contrast to pluralistic families that prioritize open discussion and individual autonomy, some families limit conversational exchange while strongly emphasizing obedience and conformity, a dynamic characteristic of the protective family communication pattern.

Protective family communication pattern is another type. Families that adopt this communication pattern are said to have high conformity but low conversation. In such families, emphases are placed on uniformity of values and attitudes, respect for authority and deliberate avoidance of conflicts that might arise as a result of disagreements. Family members are anticipated to avoid conflicts and conform to the family's interests and norms. Due to a lack of emphasis on and limited practice of communication skills, such families frequently find themselves lacking the essential abilities for constructive conflict resolution. In protective family environments, children may internalize the perception that family conversations hold minimal value, leading them to develop a sense of distrust in their own decision-making capabilities (Koerner & Fitzpatrick, 2012). From a psychosocial perspective, children raised in protective families may display external compliance but experience internal distress, such as anxiety, emotional suppression, or difficulty asserting themselves in peer interactions. Their social adjustment can be compromised, particularly in contexts where autonomy, debate, and open communication are encouraged (such as schools or universities) (Ritchie & Fitzpatrick, 2012). Without prior experience in articulating and defending personal viewpoints, these students may feel overwhelmed in environments that demand independent judgment and self-advocacy. Moreover, empirical studies (Koesten, Schrodt, & Ford, 2009) link protective communication patterns to poorer psychosocial outcomes, including greater social withdrawal, depressive symptoms, and a tendency toward emotional dependence on authority figures. Children from such family environments may also develop avoidant or anxious attachment styles, reflecting an uncertainty in interpersonal interactions where open dialogue is expected (Schrodt, Witt, & Messersmith, 2008). Whereas protective families maintain control through strict conformity and limited dialogue, an even less structured communication environment is observed in *laissez-faire* families, where both conversation and conformity are largely absent.

Laissez-faire family communication pattern is defined by low conversation orientation and low conformity orientation. Families operating under this pattern tend to place minimal emphasis on open dialogue or the enforcement of shared norms and expectations. As a result, communication within such families is often fragmented, superficial, and infrequent, with family members, especially children and young adults receiving little emotional support, guidance, or consistent feedback (Koerner & Fitzpatrick, 2012). These households typically offer limited parental involvement in decision-making and often exhibit indifference toward emotional bonding or behavioural control (Fitzpatrick & Ritchie, 1994). In terms of psychosocial adjustment, students raised in *laissez-faire* families are at risk of experiencing emotional detachment, social withdrawal, and identity confusion, largely due to the lack of nurturing communication and ambiguous familial expectations. The absence of meaningful interaction and emotional regulation in such families can hinder the development of crucial life skills such as self-esteem, empathy, emotional intelligence, and problem-solving (Koesten, Schrodt, & Ford, 2009).

Empirical studies (Schrodt & Phillips, 2006) suggest that undergraduates from *laissez-faire* families often struggle with low social competence, increased anxiety, difficulty forming meaningful relationships, and a diminished sense of self-worth. These students may feel unsupported and isolated, especially during challenging academic or social transitions, and may lack the resilience needed to cope effectively with university stressors. In extreme cases, the communication vacuum in *laissez-faire* households can contribute to maladaptive behaviours, including substance abuse or withdrawal from academic and social commitments (Hunt & Eisenberg, 2010). While some students may become independent due to the lack of family involvement, this independence is often born of necessity rather than confidence, and can mask underlying emotional struggles. Overall, the *laissez-faire* pattern is associated with weaker psychosocial adjustment outcomes, especially when compared to more engaging and structured communication styles

like consensual or pluralistic patterns. Notably, the authors claim there is no particular family typology that can be considered the best or most functional. Instead, families establish their own communication dynamics, and behaviours should be interpreted and assessed within the specific context that is unique to each family type. In spite of this argument, family communication and interaction are significant predictors of various outcomes in family members. Psychosocial adjustment in particular has been said to be significantly impacted by family communication patterns (Generous, 2016; Effiong & Usoroh, 2020; Jahromi, Mahmoodian & Samani, 2020; Price, 2023). It is therefore pertinent that the various assertions about the relationship between FCPs and psychosocial adjustment be verified for the sake of effective psychosocial counselling among undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, has increasingly become a concern. Many students struggle to engage meaningfully in academic and social activities, demonstrate low self-confidence, avoid leadership roles, exhibit poor conflict-resolution skills, and show reluctance in participating in group discussions, despite possessing the ability or knowledge to contribute. These behaviours suggest that a significant number of undergraduates face challenges in managing their emotions, building relationships, and coping with the social and psychological demands of university life. Such difficulties compromise not only their academic performance but also their emotional and social development, and they raise concern among parents, school authorities, and the wider community.

Observations and preliminary interactions indicate that these adjustment challenges may be rooted in students' family backgrounds, particularly the patterns of communication they experienced at home. Families are the first social systems where individuals learn to express emotions, handle conflicts, and develop self-concept. Certain family communication patterns that involve excessive control, emotional distance, or limited dialogue may subtly undermine a student's ability to interact confidently, assert themselves, and navigate complex social systems like the university environment. Conversely, families that encourage open discussion, expression of opinions, and shared decision-making may support healthier psychosocial adjustment.

It is against this backdrop that the researchers were concerned about the psychosocial non-adjustment of undergraduates and sought to investigate how different family communication patterns, namely, consensual, pluralistic, protective, and laissez-faire correlate with the psychosocial adjustment of students at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

Research Questions

The following research questions were stated to guide the study.

1. What is the relationship between the consensual family communication pattern and the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates?
2. What is the relationship between the pluralistic family communication pattern and the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates?
3. What is the relationship between the protective family communication pattern and the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates?
4. What is the relationship between the laissez-faire family communication pattern and psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance.

1. Consensual family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates.
2. Pluralistic family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates.
3. Protective family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates.

4. Laissez-faire family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design for the study was the correlational survey design. The area of study of this research was the Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. The population of this study was 25,843 undergraduates from eight Faculties. The sample for the study was 394 undergraduates arrived at using Glenn (1994) formula for selecting sample size. The Family Communication Patterns Questionnaire (FCPQ) and Undergraduates’ Psychosocial Adjustment Scale (UPAS) both developed by the researchers were administered to collect data. The instruments were validated by experts in Guidance and Counselling and Science and Mathematics Education, and yielded reliability coefficients of 0.746 and 0.754 respectively. Both instruments followed the modified Likert four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options have numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to answer research questions. Similarly, PPMC was also used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between the consensual family communication pattern and the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi?*

Table 1: Correlation Between Consensual Family Communication Pattern and Psychosocial Adjustment of Undergraduates.

Variables		Consensual FCP	Psychosocial Adjustment
Consensual FCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.516**
	N	394	394
Psychosocial Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.516**	1
	N	394	394

Table 1 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for consensual family communication pattern (FCP) and psychosocial adjustment. Results indicate a moderate positive correlation, $r = .516$, suggesting that high levels of consensual communication in families are associated with greater psychosocial adjustment among undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between the pluralistic family communication pattern and psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi?*

Table 2: Correlation Between Pluralistic Family Communication Pattern and Psychosocial Adjustment of Undergraduates.

Variables		Pluralistic FCP	Psychosocial Adjustment
Pluralistic FCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.573**
	N	394	394
Psychosocial Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.573**	1
	N	394	394

Table 2 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for pluralistic family communication pattern (FCP) and psychosocial adjustment. Results indicate a moderately positive correlation, $r = .573$, suggesting that higher levels of pluralistic communication in families are associated with greater psychosocial adjustment among undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between the protective family communication pattern and the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi?*

Table 3: Correlation Between Protective Family Communication Pattern and Psychosocial Adjustment of Undergraduates.

Variables		Protective FCP	Psychosocial Adjustment
Protective FCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.459**
	N	394	394
Psychosocial Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.459**	1
	N	394	394

Table 3 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for protective FCP and psychosocial adjustment. Results indicate a weak positive correlation $r = .459$, suggesting that protective FCP in families is associated with psychosocial adjustment among undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi but weakly.

Research Question 4: *What is the relationship between the laissez-faire family communication pattern and psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi?*

Table 4: Correlation Between Laissez-Faire Family Communication Pattern and Psychosocial Adjustment of Undergraduates.

Variables		Laissez-faire FCP	Psychosocial Adjustment
Laissez-faire FCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.442**
	N	394	394
Psychosocial Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.442**	1
	N	394	394

Table 4 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for laissez-faire family communication pattern (FCP) and psychosocial adjustment. Results indicate a weak positive correlation, $r = .442$, suggesting that even though laissez-faire communication is less structured, there is still a positive association between this pattern and psychosocial adjustment among undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. However, the relationship is weaker compared to other communication patterns, indicating that laissez-faire communication may be less effective in promoting strong psychosocial adjustment.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was also used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Consensual family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation for Consensual Family Communication Pattern and Psychosocial Adjustment Among Undergraduates.

Variables		Consensual FCP	Psychosocial Adjustment
Consensual FCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.516**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	394	394
Psychosocial Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.516**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	394	394

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 5 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for consensual FCP and psychosocial adjustment. Results indicate a significant moderate positive correlation $r = .516$, $p < .05$, suggesting that high levels of consensual communication in families are associated with greater psychosocial adjustment among undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that consensual family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi is rejected. This implies that consensual family communication pattern has significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

Hypothesis 2

Pluralistic family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment Correlation for Family Communication Pattern and Psychosocial Adjustment of Undergraduates.

Variables		Pluralistic FCP	Psychosocial Adjustment
Pluralistic FCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.573**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	394	394
Psychosocial Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.573**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	394	394

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 6 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for pluralistic FCP and psychosocial adjustment. Results indicate a significant moderate positive correlation $r = .573$, $p < .05$, suggesting that higher levels of pluralistic communication in families are associated with greater psychosocial adjustment among undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that pluralistic family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi is rejected. This implies that pluralistic family communication pattern has significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

Hypothesis 3

Protective family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

Table 7: Pearson Product Moment Correlation for Family Communication Pattern and Psychosocial Adjustment of Undergraduates.

Variables		Protective FCP	Psychosocial Adjustment
Protective FCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.459**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	394	394
Psychosocial Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.459**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	394	394

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 7 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for protective FCP and psychosocial adjustment. Results indicate a significant weak positive correlation $r = .459$, $p < .05$, suggesting that protective FCP in families is associated with psychosocial adjustment among undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi but weakly. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that

protective family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi is rejected. This implies that protective family communication pattern has significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

Hypothesis 4

Laissez-faire family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

Table 8: Pearson Product Moment Correlation for Family Communication Pattern and Psychosocial Adjustment of Undergraduates.

Variables		Laissez-faire FCP	Psychosocial Adjustment
Laissez-faire FCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.442**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	394	394
Psychosocial Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.442**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	394	394

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 8 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for laissez-faire FCP and psychosocial adjustment. Results indicate a significant weak positive correlation $r = .442$, $p < .05$, suggesting that laissez-faire FCP in families is associated weakly with psychosocial adjustment among undergraduates at Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that laissez-faire family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi is rejected. This implies that laissez-faire family communication pattern has significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first research question examined the relationship between the consensual family communication pattern and the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates. The finding of the study revealed that there is a moderate positive relationship between consensual family communication pattern and psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. In line with this result, the corresponding hypothesis, which stated that consensual family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates, was rejected. This finding implies that undergraduates who were socialized in families that encouraged open discussion while maintaining shared values and parental guidance are better psychologically and socially equipped to adapt to university life. Consensual family communication is characterized by a balance between open dialogue and parental authority, where family members are encouraged to freely express their thoughts and feelings while still respecting shared norms, values, and guidance provided by parents. Such an environment fosters emotional security, mutual respect, and effective interpersonal skills, which are essential for navigating the complex social and academic demands of university life. Undergraduates from consensual families are therefore more likely to exhibit emotional stability, self-confidence, empathy, and constructive problem-solving skills, enabling them to cope effectively with academic pressures, peer relationships, and transitional challenges associated with emerging adulthood. Furthermore, the moderate strength of the relationship suggests that while consensual family communication is an important contributor to psychosocial adjustment, it operates alongside other contextual and individual factors such as peer influence, institutional support, personality traits, and socio-economic conditions. Nonetheless, the significance of the relationship underscores the enduring relationship that exists between family-of-origin communication patterns and psychosocial adjustment even as students gain independence in the

university setting. This finding is strongly supported by Zarnaghash, Zarnaghash, and Zarnaghash (2013), whose study revealed that conversation-oriented family communication patterns, which include consensual communication, were significant predictors of students' psychological health, which is one aspect of psychosocial adjustment. Similarly, Heidari, Mortezaee, Masomi, and Raji (2018) found a significant positive relationship between conversation orientation and adolescents' mental health, with consensual families ranking high in promoting positive mental health outcomes. In the same vein, Effiong and Usoroh (2020) reported that consensual family communication was associated with closeness, cooperation, and cohesion among adolescents and parents, all of which are psychosocial attributes that are closely linked to effective psychosocial adjustment. These findings collectively reinforce the present result by demonstrating that consensual family environments foster communication skills and emotional security that promote psychosocial adjustment.

The second research question sought to determine the relationship between the pluralistic family communication pattern and the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates. The finding revealed that pluralistic family communication pattern has a moderate positive relationship with psychosocial adjustment, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis which stated that pluralistic family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment. This finding implies that undergraduates who were raised in pluralistic family environments characterized by high levels of open communication, encouragement of free expression of ideas, and minimal emphasis on rigid conformity are more likely to exhibit healthier psychosocial adjustment in the university. In such families, children are socialized to express their opinions, question ideas respectfully, and participate actively in family decision-making, which fosters autonomy, self-efficacy, and strong interpersonal skills. These qualities are particularly valuable in the university setting, where students are required to engage in independent learning, interact with diverse peers, and adapt to new social and academic expectations. As a result, undergraduates from pluralistic families tend to demonstrate greater social competence, emotional regulation, assertiveness, and confidence in interpersonal interactions, thereby enhancing their overall psychosocial adjustment. The moderate positive relationship further suggests that pluralistic communication plays a substantial, though not exclusive, role in shaping students' psychosocial functioning. This result aligns with the findings of Fard (2020), who found that pluralistic communication patterns had a positive and significant relationship with adjustment and resiliency among children, indicating that open family discussions foster adaptive coping skills. Further support is provided by Nakhaee, Vagharseyyedin, Afkar, and Mood (2017), who found that adolescents from pluralistic families demonstrated significantly higher assertiveness than those from protective or laissez-faire families. These findings collectively substantiate the present study's result by showing that pluralistic family communication enhances psychosocial attributes essential for effective adjustment in the university.

The third research question examined the relationship between the protective family communication pattern and the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates. The finding of the study revealed that the protective family communication pattern has a weak positive relationship with the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis stating that protective family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment. This finding suggests that while protective family environments may contribute marginally to psychosocial adjustment by providing structure, clear rules, parental control, and moral guidance, their heavy emphasis on conformity and obedience, coupled with limited open dialogue, constrains the development of essential psychosocial skills. In protective families, offspring are often expected to accept parental decisions without question, which may limit opportunities for emotional expression, critical thinking, and autonomous decision-making. As undergraduates transition into the university environment where independence, self-regulation, and interpersonal negotiation are required such restrictions may undermine their ability to cope effectively with psychosocial demands. The weak positive nature of the relationship further indicates that the benefits derived from protective communication patterns are minimal and may be overshadowed by their potential drawbacks. This finding is consistent with Jahromi, Mahmoodian, and Samani (2020) who found a

significant negative relationship between protective communication patterns and adjustment among high school students, indicating that high conformity undermines adaptive functioning. Additionally, Price (2023) demonstrated that high conformity orientation which particularly covers protective family communication pattern predicted emotional suppression and maladaptive coping behaviours among young adults, outcomes that are detrimental to psychosocial adjustment. These studies support the weak association observed in the present study, suggesting that protective family communication may contribute minimally or even negatively to psychosocial wellbeing.

The fourth research question addressed the relationship between the laissez-faire family communication pattern and the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates. The finding of the study revealed that the laissez-faire family communication pattern has a weak positive relationship with the psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, which resulted in the rejection of the null hypothesis stating that laissez-faire family communication pattern has no significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment. This finding suggests that although laissez-faire family environments may allow a degree of personal freedom and independence due to minimal parental control and expectations, the absence of consistent communication, emotional support, and guidance limits their effectiveness in fostering healthy psychosocial development. In such families, interaction among members is often infrequent, superficial, or fragmented, leaving offspring to navigate emotional and social challenges largely on their own. The weak positive relationship observed indicates that any perceived benefits of independence associated with laissez-faire communication are insufficient to substantially enhance psychosocial adjustment. Undergraduates from these family backgrounds may develop a form of independence that is situational or forced rather than psychologically grounded, which may mask underlying difficulties such as poor emotional regulation, low self-esteem, feelings of isolation, and difficulty forming stable interpersonal relationships. This result is supported by Effiong and Usoroh (2020), who found that laissez-faire family communication patterns were associated with lack of cohesion and reduced cooperation within families. Similarly, Izuchi and Onwukwe (2021) reported that adolescents from families lacking conversation orientation exhibited lower psychosocial adjustment scores, regardless of gender. These findings reinforce the present result by highlighting the negative psychosocial implications of emotionally detached and poorly structured family communication environments like laissez-faire family communication pattern.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated family communication patterns as correlates of psychosocial adjustment of undergraduates in Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi, as well as the moderating roles of gender and marital status. The findings revealed that consensual and pluralistic family communication patterns had significant moderate positive relationships with psychosocial adjustment, indicating that undergraduates raised in families characterized by open dialogue, emotional support, and shared decision-making tend to exhibit better emotional stability, social competence, and adaptive coping skills. In contrast, protective and laissez-faire family communication patterns showed significant but weak positive relationships with psychosocial adjustment, suggesting that while these patterns may offer some level of structure or independence, their restrictive or disengaged nature limits optimal psychosocial development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Given the significant moderate positive relationship between consensual family communication pattern and psychosocial adjustment, it is recommended that parents and guardians adopt communication practices that encourage open discussion while maintaining clear family values and guidance.
2. In view of the significant moderate positive relationship between pluralistic family communication pattern and psychosocial adjustment, families should be encouraged to foster environments that support free expression of ideas, independent thinking, and mutual respect.

3. Considering that the protective family communication pattern showed a significant but weak positive relationship with psychosocial adjustment, it is recommended that parents who emphasize control and conformity gradually integrate more open communication and emotional expression into family interactions.
4. Given the significant but weak positive relationship between laissez-faire family communication pattern and psychosocial adjustment, families should be sensitized to the importance of active parental involvement and emotional guidance in students' developmental experiences.

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